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CHARACTERISTICS OF CONSENSUS ALGORITHMS IN
INCREASING DATA RELIABILITY

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Abstract. The emergence and improvement of various distributed systems, the development and improvement of various types of consensus algorithms are demanding. Consensus algorithms in distributed systems have different characteristics and functions. In this research work, we will first distinguish two main types of consensus algorithms and then describe their characteristics.

Keywords: Encouraging consensus, Blockchain systems, Authentication, Attack vectors.

Encouraging consensus. Some consensus algorithms reward nodes in the system for creating and adding a new block to the blockchain system. These algorithms are active mainly in cryptocurrency systems, because the transactions made on cryptocurrency are also useful for other users.

Figure 1. Characteristics of consensus algorithms.

Unincentivized Consensus. In some blockchain systems, as a result of the

creation and addition of a new block to the blockchain, no incentive mechanism is used for the participating nodes in the system. This type of consensus algorithm does not rely on any reward mechanism, because only authorized nodes can participate in the process of creating blocks of the consensus algorithm [1].

Consensus characteristics. In distributed systems, consensus algorithms have different characteristics and serve different purposes. To compare different groups of consensus algorithms, we need to define evaluation criteria. In the research paper, we present the evaluation criteria in the form of taxonomies of the characteristics of consensus algorithms [3].

Structural characteristics. The structural characteristics of consensus define how the various nodes in the blockchain system are configured to participate in the consensus algorithm. These characteristics can be divided into the following different categories.

Node Types: In this, the consensus algorithm follows the different types of nodes that must be involved in order to achieve consensus. The types depend on the consensus algorithm presented in the next section.

Structure Type: This is done based on the way different nodes are structured within a consensus algorithm using the concept of a system. The structure of the system itself can be of two types: one and several partial systems [2].

Basic Mechanism: Consensus algorithm follows a specific mechanism used to validate a particular node. It is possible in cryptosystems using a probability mechanism based on cryptography or other random mechanisms.

Safety characteristics. Consensus algorithms must meet a number of security characteristics, as shown in Figure 2, and those characteristics are described as follows:

Figure 2. Security characteristics of consensus algorithms.

Authentication: This process refers to the need to properly verify or authenticate the nodes participating in the consensus protocol.

Non-repudiation: This process indicates that the consensus protocol supports non-repudiation. In this case, the non-repudiation function is activated if certain transactions are not completed successfully.

Attack vectors: This characteristic refers to the attack vectors applied to the consensus mechanism. Attack vectors are applied to a certain class of consensus algorithm [1]. Consensus algorithms should make it possible to eliminate possible attack vectors.

Consensus algorithms are a key feature of security and reliability in blockchain-based systems. To ensure security and reliability, the above three features are required to be enabled.

Conclusion.

Currently, the sharp increase in information flows makes quality processing of these data and increasing their security urgent. Application of blockchain-based mechanisms in information systems and payment systems in computer networks leads to higher efficiency. The main indicators of blockchain-based systems are its consensus algorithms.

References

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